

Characterization of Porous CFRP Laminates by Mechanical Testing and X-ray Computed Tomography

Antonios G. STAMOPOULOS¹, Konstantinos I. TSERPES¹, Petr PRUCHA², Daniel VAVRIK³

¹Laboratory of Technology and Strength of Materials, Department of Mechanical Engineering and Aeronautics, University of Patras, Patras 26 500, Greece, Phone: +30 2610 969498, E-mail: kit2005@mech.upatras.gr, a.stam@mech.upatras.gr

²LA Composite, Beranovych 65, 199 02 Prague 9, Czech Republic, E-mail: prucha@lacomposite.com

³Institute of Experimental and Applied Physics, Czech Technical University in Prague, Horska 3a/22, Prague, - Czech Republic, E-mail: vavrik@itam.cas.cz

Abstract

In the present work, the effects of porosity on matrix-dominated mechanical properties of unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) composites were evaluated by mechanical testing and X-ray computed tomography (CT). Four different levels of porosity in the CFRP material were achieved by implementing different manufacturing parameters. Samples taken from the plates, from which specimens were cut, were tested using X-ray CT to detect porosity. The quantification of porosity from the CT scans was performed using the VG Studio Max software. Four different mechanical tests were conducted, namely, transverse tension, 3-point bending, short beam shear and v-notched rail shear tests. The experimental results reveal that the presence of porosity degrades the transverse strength and shear properties of the CFRP material. The amount of degradation depends mainly on the volume fraction of the pores, however, in some cases, a dependence on the size of pores was found.

Keywords: CFRP material, porosity, defects, mechanical testing, X-ray computed tomography

1. Introduction

The defects introduced in composite materials during the manufacturing process present a form of initial damage for the component. The most common manufacturing defect in composite materials is “porosity”, the presence of voids in the matrix. Porosity under certain circumstances can be critical as it could degrade the already low matrix-dominated properties [1-5], thus making the composite component more prone to fatigue and impact. It is therefore very important to detect porosity in composite components before introducing them to service and define critical porosity characteristics by evaluating the effects of porosity on the mechanical properties of the composite material.

The most widely used method for the detection of porosity is ultrasonic testing which is a 2D method with a quite limited accuracy. In recent years, the X-ray computed tomography (CT) serves as the most advanced and detailed non-destructive technique for the detection and quantification of defects with its most important advantage being the 3D representation. There are only few works that have employed CT to characterize porosity in carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRPs). In [6] X-ray tomography was used to observe and describe the void nucleation and coalescence in metal matrix composites while in [7] systematic CT investigations on a broad variety of composite samples with different measurement parameters were performed and the results were compared with results obtained from standard porosity measurement methods.

The aim of the present work is to combine mechanical testing and CT characterization in order to correlate the characteristics of porosity (volume fraction, size, and shape) with the decrease in the matrix-dominated mechanical properties of CFRP composites.

2. Manufacturing

The specimens used were made from prepreg composite material cured at elevated temperature and pressure in an autoclave. For the reinforcement, HTA 24k carbon fibers were used. The weight resin content in the prepreg was 35%. Each panel was manufactured from equal number of prepreg plies. The panels were cured in an autoclave using different curing cycles to achieve the different porosity levels. All curing cycles had the same temperature and dwell on the curing temperature. The different porosity levels were achieved by applying a different pressure inside the autoclave. Samples with four levels of porosity have been manufactured, namely reference, minimum porosity, medium porosity and extensive porosity samples. The common temperature cycle and the different applied pressure cycles applied for each porosity level are shown in Fig.1.

Figure 1: Applied temperature and pressure cycles.

3. X-ray CT inspection

After manufacturing, small samples were cut from the plates and used for porosity evaluation via X-ray CT. The measurements were taken using an X-ray WorX tube, XWT 240 SE and flat panel detector Perkin Elmer XRD 1622. The data were acquired with the following parameters: 800 projections, X-ray tube at 70 kV and 300 μ A, focus to detector distance 1335 mm, focus to object distance 73 mm, acquisition time of 1 sec, voxel size of 11 μ m. The projection data were corrected for beam hardening effect by the signal to equivalent thickness method [8]. The images were acquired and reconstructed using the Voxel 6 software provided by the Fraunhofer Development Centre X-ray Technology, EZRT in Furth, Germany.

The CT scan data were analysed using the VG Studio MAX software [9] by means of surface determination, local regions of interest and defect analysis features such as the Enhanced v2.1 algorithm. A parametric study was performed in order to assess the effects of lower detected values and probability thresholds on the porosity analysis. The values of porosity volume fraction, estimated by the program for two voxel sizes, are listed in Table 1 together with values obtained by the chemical decomposition method.

In the reference case, some very small pores (0.8%) and a few large needle-shaped pores (0.02%) indicated by arrows in Fig.2a were found. With increasing the porosity level, the

number and size of the large pores increase significantly and the numbers of small pores increase considerably. As shown in Fig.2b in the extensive porosity case the specimen contains large needle-shaped pores and pores with considerable volume whose shape deviates from the needle shape.

Table 1: Porosity volume fraction.

Sample (porosity level)	Porosity volume fraction (CT-VG Studio MAX)		Porosity volume fraction (chemical decomposition)
	Voxel size: 8	Voxel size: 4	
Reference	0.82 %	1.52 %	4.46 %
Minimum	1.56 %	3.62 %	5.31 %
Medium	1.62 %	3.87 %	5.89 %
Extensive	3.43 %	5.12 %	11 %

Figure 2: Projection images from VG Studio MAX: a. Reference sample, b. Extensive porosity sample.

The deviation between the measurements taken from CT (analysis with VG Studio MAX) and the chemical decomposition method lies in the presence of micro-pores in the matrix that exceed the lowest detectable values of CT; with decreasing the voxel size, the values of porosity volume fraction evaluated by the program approach the values measured by the chemical decomposition method.

Figs. 3 to 6 plot the defect volume distribution of the samples against the different porosity levels. In the reference sample, there are many small volume pores. In the minimum porosity sample, the number of pores decreases by an order of magnitude but their volume increases by an order of magnitude compared to the reference sample. Moving from the minimum to the medium porosity samples, the number of pores remains quite the same, however, the volume of the few big pores increase but not considerably. This explains the similar porosity volume fractions between the two levels. Finally, in the extensive porosity sample, there are a few pores but with a volume two orders of magnitude larger than that of the medium porosity level.

Figure 3: Defect volume distribution for the reference sample.

Figure 4: Defect volume distribution for the minimum porosity sample.

Figure 5: Defect volume distribution for the medium porosity sample.

Figure 6: Defect volume distribution for the extensive porosity sample.

4. Mechanical testing

For assessing the effect of porosity on the matrix-dominated mechanical properties of the CFRP material, four different types of tests were appropriately selected. All tests were conducted using an MTS 100 kN universal testing machine. In the following sections, the experimental procedures are described and the experimental results are presented and discussed in relation with CT data of porosity.

4.1 Transverse tensile test

Transverse tensile tests were conducted on unidirectional $[90^\circ]_{16}$ specimens according to the ASTM D3039 standard [14] to measure the transverse stiffness and transverse tensile strength

of the prepreg ply. These properties are dominated by the matrix, thus they are presumably affected by porosity. Five specimens were tested from each samples category. Fig.7 shows a photo of a specimen mounted on the machine during a transverse test.

The average experimental transverse stiffness and strength values are presented for the samples of the different porosity level in Fig.8a and Fig.8b, respectively. The stiffness was derived from the slope of the linear part of the stress-strain curve and the strength from the maximum recorded load. The experimental results show a slight decrease in transverse stiffness, which was expected due to the small volume fraction of the pores. On the contrary, there is a considerable decrease in transverse strength of the ply, which reaches up to 14.7% for the case of extensive porosity. The fact that the amount of decrease in transverse strength of the CFRP ply is not linearly related to the porosity volume fraction reveals the effect of pores' size and shape. In the case of extensive porosity sample, the large transverse needle-shaped pores act like cracks which grow forming larger macro-cracks that cause early failure of the specimen.

Figure 7: Photo of a transverse test in progress.

Figure 8: Average experimental transverse stiffness (a) and strength (b) of samples with different porosity level.

4.2 Three-point bending test

The 3-point bending (flexural) tests were conducted according to ISO 14125:1998 standard [15]. Five rectangular unidirectional $[0^{\circ}]_{16}$ specimens were tested for each porosity level using the appropriate test fixture. The properties measured from this test are the flexural strength, flexural modulus. All specimens failed in the mid-span section, thus they are considered to be valid. Fig.9a shows a photo of a specimen mounted on the machine during testing and Fig.9b shows a photo of a close-view of the failed area (mid-span) of a specimen.

According to [15] the flexural strength of the specimen is given by

$$\sigma_f = \frac{3FL}{2bh^2} \quad (1)$$

where F is the maximum recorded force, b , h and L are the width, height and length of the specimen, respectively. The flexural modulus is given by

$$E_f = 500(\sigma_f'' - \sigma_f') \quad (2)$$

where σ_f'' , σ_f' is the flexural strength at deflection of 0.05% and 0.25%, respectively.

Figure 9: a. Photo of a specimen failed due to 3-point bending, b. Close-view of the mid-span cracked area.

The average experimental flexural modulus and strength values of the samples with different porosity level are presented in Fig.10a and Fig.10b, respectively. As can be seen, there is a decrease in both the flexural modulus and strength. The decrease in strength reaches for the extensive porosity samples the value of 17.4%. Comparing these findings with the findings of transverse tests, it is concluded that porosity affects the shear load carrying capability of the material in a larger degree than does for the tensile load. The fact that the flexural modulus and strength of the medium porosity samples is lower than the ones of the minimum porosity samples is an indirect indication of the severe effect of large volume pores on the load-carrying capability of the material.

Figure 10: Average experimental flexural modulus (a) and flexural strength (b) of samples with different porosity level.

4.3. Short beam shear strength (ILSS)

The short beam shear test is a 3-point bending test, however, it is conducted with a shorter and much thicker specimen than does the classical 3-point bending test. The specimen of the

ILSS test has been properly designed so as high interlaminar shear stresses to be developed thus allowing for a more global assessment of the effect of porosity on the shear behavior of the CFRP laminate. The ILSS tests were conducted according to ASTM D2344M standard [16]. Five samples were tested for each porosity level. Due to the large thickness and small length the stress state in the ILSS specimen is not pure shear. The short beam strength of the specimens was derived from

$$F_{sbs} = 0.75 \times \frac{P_m}{b \times h} \quad (3)$$

where P_m is the maximum load, b is specimen's width and h is the specimen's length.

The average experimental short beam strength values of the samples with different porosity level are presented in Fig.11b. The results show a considerable decrease in the short beam strength which is an indication of the negative effect of porosity on the interlaminar shear properties of the CFRP laminates. The similarity in the values obtained for the medium and extensive porosity levels and the large standard deviation of the medium porosity level are due to the effect of pores location with regard to the critically loaded areas in the specimen.

Figure 11: a. Photo of a specimen just before an ILSS test, b. Average experimental short beam strength of samples with different porosity level.

4.4 V-notched rail shear test

The v-notched rail shear test is a combination of the Iosipescu and Rail shear tests. This test is suitable for determining shear properties. In the present work, the lay-up of 0° was chosen such as to determine the in-plane shear modulus and shear strength of the CFRP material. The tests were conducted according to ASTM D7078 standard [17]. Five samples were tested from each porosity level category. Fig.12a shows a specimen with the strain gauges mounted on it. In all tests, two cracks started from the notches and several cracks were deployed in the area close to the strain gauges and along the fibres direction as shown in Fig.12b.

The average experimental in-plane shear modulus and strength of the samples with different porosity level are presented in Fig.13a and Fig.13b, respectively. The shear modulus was derived from the slope of the linear part of the shear stress-shear strain curve while the shear strength from the maximum recorded force. A significant decrease in both properties due to porosity is observed. This verifies the findings of sections 4.2 and 4.3 that porosity affects significantly the shear load-carrying capability of the composite material from the very early stages of loading. The large standard deviation in the in-plane shear modulus of the first three categories is an indication of the different dispersion of the pores in the samples with regard to the critically loaded areas in the specimen.

Figure 12: a. Photo of a v-notched rail shear specimen ready to be tested, b. Photo of a cracked v-notched rail shear specimen.

Figure 13: Average experimental flexural modulus (a) and flexural strength (b) of samples with different porosity level.

5. Conclusions

In this work, the effects of porosity on the mechanical properties of CFRP composites were evaluated by mechanical testing and X-ray CT. From the combined study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The presence of porosity does not affect the transverse stiffness of the CFRP ply as it does not affect the tensile load-carrying capability of the matrix at low load levels. On the contrary, it leads, even at a low content, to the significant decrease in transverse tensile strength of the CFRP ply since at higher load levels the pores act like cracks that coalesce with each other forming larger pores.
- The presence of porosity, even at a small content, degrades the shear load-carrying capability of the ply from low load levels causing a decrease in the in-plane shear moduli, in-plane shear strength and short beam strength which is as measure of interlaminar shear strength.
- Between the minimum and medium porosity levels, which have the same porosity volume fraction, it was found that the medium porosity level is more severe for the shear properties of the CFRP laminate as it contains larger pores.
- The large standard deviation observed in some tests is an indirect indication of the effect of pores' location. The study of this effect is currently under investigation by the authors by performing additional analyses on the information obtained from VG Studio MAX software.

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